

ISic1004

I.Sicily inscription 1004

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 118

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Φορτουνᾶτα
2. ζήσασα ἔτη κ
3. ἔτελεύτησεν
4. τῆ̄ πρὸ ε καλ(ανδῶν)
5. Φεβρ(ουαρίων) ἐνθά
6. δε κῖτε

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation

Commentary

Text on reverse of same stone is ISic0009 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0999>]

Digital identifiers:

TM 492631

EDCS 39102158

PHI 140482

Bibliography

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Ferrua, A 1941. Epigrafica sicula pagana e cristiana. *Rivista di archeologia cristiana*. 18: 151-243. At no.25

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